

CHARLZ DIKKENSNING “KATTA UMIDLAR” ROMANIDA BOSH QAHRAMON RUHIY OLAMI

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada 19-asr ingliz adabiyotida yorqin iz qoldirgan Charlz Dikenzning “Katta umidlar” asari bosh qahramoni ruhiyati tasviri haqida so‘z yuritilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: roman, qahramon, ruhiyat, ingliz, kechinma, munosabat, realism.

Abstract. The presented article talks about the depiction of the main character’s psyche in *Great Expectations* by the English writer Charles Dickens.

Key words: novel, character, English, inner world, relations, realism, thoughts.

Kirish. Qachonki inson kamoloti haqida so‘z ketganda adabiyotni tilga olmasdan ilojimiz yo‘q. Ayniqsa, insonning inson ekanligi, uning boshqa jonzotlardan o‘zining faqat o‘zidagina bor hislatlari bilan ajralib turishini ko‘rsatishda, albatta, badiiy adabiyotning o‘rni beqiyosdir. O‘zining ana shunday asarlari bilan nafaqat ingliz, balki butun dunyo kitobxonlari mehrini qozongan adiblardan biri ingliz yozuvchisi Charlz Dikens(1812-1870)dir. U yashagan davr Angliyada qirolicha Viktoriya davri(1837-1901)ga to‘g‘ri keldi va adib bu davr mamlakat ijtimoiy hayotidagi har xil muammolar: sinfiy tabaqalanish, adolatsizlik, jabr –zulmni ochiq-oydin o‘z asarlarida aks ettiradi [1]. Yozuvchining shunday asarlaridan biri “Katta umidlar” asaridir. Asarda qahramonlar taqdiri misolida jamiyatdagi keskin muammolardan biri ijtimoiy tengsizlik yoritiladi. Shuningdek, muallif sof insoniy tuyg‘ular boylik va obro‘-e‘tibordan ustun turishini isbotlamoqchi bo‘ladi, go‘yoki. Ushbu so‘zlar muallifning quyidagi hikmatli gapida o‘z tasdig‘ini topadi: “*A loving heart is the truest wisdom.*”- *Sevaoladigan yurak haqiqiy donolik.* [2]

Asosiy qism. “Katta umidlar” shu (*Great Expectations*, 1860) asari atrofdagilarga va o‘ziga Pip nomi bilan mashhur bo‘lgan Philip Pirripning kambag‘allikdan to haqiqiy jentlmen darajasigacha bo‘lgan yo‘ldagi o‘sishi, rivojlanishi, inson sifatida shakllanishini hikoya qiladi. Pip asosiy qahramon bo‘lib, qolgan barcha voqealar va obrazlar uning atrofida birlashadi. Shuning uchun ham uning shaxsiyatini tushunish asar mazmunini tushunishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Asarda ikkita Pipni uchratamiz: biri voqealarga o‘zining munosabati va qarashlari bilan kitobxonning fikrlari rivojlanishida yordam beradigan hikoyachi, ikkinchisi esa shu voqealar markazida turuvchi, yosh, tajribasiz, sodda qahramon.

Buyuk Britaniyalik yozuvchi Ben asar haqida:

“*Pip obrazi hikoyadagi asosiy qahramondir. Bu kitob yosh qahramonning bolaligidan to ulg‘ayishiga bo‘lgan sayohati sifatida bizga ma‘lum*”.– deydi. [2.]

Amerikalik olim Thomas.E.Connolly esa Pip va asar haqida shunday deydi: “*Shunday qilib Pip hayotining uch bosqichini o‘rganar ekanmiz, biz nafaqat uning umidlari va umidsizliklari, balki, butun 19-asrni qamrab olgan umumiy bezovtalik haqida ham o‘ylashimiz kerak. Bu parvenuning hayoti. Biz Pipning hayoti haqidagi hikoyani o‘sha apytdagi jamiyatni yolg‘on, uydirma, da‘vogarlik va ijtimoiy buzqlik girdobiga aylantirgan boylik xissining ijtimoiy tanqidi sifatida ko‘rib chiqishimiz kerak.* [3.]

Bosh qahramon ota-onasini ko‘rmagan va Jo ismli temirchiga turmushga chiqqan yolg‘iz opasi qo‘lida tarbiya topgan. Aynan o‘sha temirchi Pipga o‘zining opasidan ko‘ra mehribonroq va hamdard sherikdir. Jo Pipning eng yaqin do‘sti, chunki faqatgina u Pipni tushuna oladi va har qachon Pipni opasining g‘azabidan ogohlantirish orqali uni jazodan qutqarib qoladi. Bir kuni Jo o‘zining boshidan o‘tkazganlarini hamda Pipni qanday asrab olishganlarini unga aytib beradi. Buni eshitgan Pipda Joga nisbatan hurmat yanada kuchayadi. Buni hikoyachi shunday izohlaydi: *“We were equals afterwards, as we had been before; but, afterwards at quiet times when I sat looking at Joe and thinking about him, I had a new sensation of feeling conscious that I was looking up to Joe in my heart.”* [4.]

“Biz avvalgidek do‘stlar edik, lekin tinchgina Joga qarab u haqida o‘ylab o‘tirganimda men Joni chin dildan hurmat qila boshlaganimni sezdim.”

Afsuski, sodda, dunyoni torroq doirada his qiluvchi, barcha narsalarni osonroq tushunishni xohlaydigan bosh qahramon go‘zal qiz Estellani uchratgandan so‘ng barchasi o‘zgara boshlaydi. Unda “katta umidlar” paydo bo‘la boshlaydi, ya‘ni omadli, boy va haqiqiy janob bo‘lish, shu orqali qizning muhabbatini qozonish. Shu yo‘lda u Londonga ko‘chib o‘tib o‘qishni va o‘rganishni boshlaydi. So‘ngra ana shu o‘ziga eng yaqin insonlardan bo‘lgan Joga va murabbiysi Biddiya nisbatan noto‘g‘ri munosabatda bo‘ladi. Bir kuni Pip Biddiydan Joning o‘zining oldiga kelayotgani to‘g‘risida xat oladi. Pipning munosabatini hikoyachi shunday keltiradi:

“I received this letter by the post on Monday morning, and therefore its appointment was for next day, Let me confess exactly, with what feelings I looked forward to Joe’s coming. Not with pleasure, though I was bound to him by so many ties; no; with considerable disturbance, some mortification, and a keen sense of incongruity. If I could have kept him away by paying money; I certainly would have paid money” [5.] - *“Men bu xatni pochta orqali dushanba kuni ertalab oldim va shuning uchun uchrashuv keyingi kuni bo‘ldi. Ruxsatingiz bilan qanday hissiyotlarni his qilganimni aytsam. Men Joga juda ko‘p rishtalar bilan bog‘langanimga qaramasdan, hursandchilik bilan emas, balki sezilarli bezovtalik, biroz ung‘aysizlik va kuchli noodatiylik hissi bilan. Agar men uni pul to‘lab uzoqlashtira olsam, aniq pul to‘lagan bo‘lar edim.”*

Pipning bu xatni quvonch bilan emas, aksincha tashvish va xavotir bilan qabul qilishi yuqoridagi fikrimizga dalil bo‘la oladi. Nima uchun u o‘zining eng yaqin insoniga nisbatan bunday munosabatda bo‘ldi? o‘z-o‘zidan shunday savol tug‘iladi kitobxonda. Bunga bosh qahramon shunday izoh beradi: *“As I had grown accustomed to my expectations, I had insensibly begun to notice their effect upon myself and those around me. Their influence on my own character; I disguised from my recognition as much as possible, but I knew very well that it was not all good. I lived in a state of chronic uneasiness respecting my behavior to Joe.”* [6.]

“Umidlarimga ko‘nikib o‘sganim sababli ularning o‘zimga va atrofimdagilarga ta’sirini seza boshladim. Men iloji boricha o‘zimni bilmagandek tutdim, lekin bu yaxshi emasligini juda yaqqol his qilardim. Men Joga bo‘lgan munosabatim haqida surunkali tashvish bilan yashadim.”

Bu so‘zlardan ayonki, Pipning orzu-istaklari uning atrofdagi insonlarga, xususan, Joga nisbatan munosabatining o‘zgarishida asosiy omil bo‘la oladi. Ammo uning ko‘ngliga taskin berib turuvchi narsa bor edi: U boy va haqiqiy jentelmen bo‘ladi va Estellani muhabbatiga erishadi. Vaholanki, hayotda har doim ham orzular amalga oshavermaydi. Pip haqiqatni ya‘ni uni moliyaviy jihatdan qo‘llab-quvvatlayotgan odam boshqaligini, Estellaga hech qachon yetishaolmasligini bilganda qanchalik katta xatoga yo‘l qo‘yganligini anglaydi. U shunday izoh beradi: *“I would not have gone back to Joe now; I would not have gone to Biddy now for any consideration: simply, I*

suppose, because my sense of my own worthlrs conduct to them was greater than every consideration. No wisdom on earth could have given me the comfort that I should have derived from their simplicity and fidelity;but I could never, never, undo what I had done.” [7] - “Hozir men istalgan mulohaza uchun ham Joning oldiga ham, Biddiying oldiga ham boraolmagan bo‘lar edim. Shunchaki, o‘zining ularga nisbatan foydasiz xatti-harakatlarimni his qilishim har qanday fikrdan ustunroq edi. Yer yuzidagi hech bir donolik menga ularning soddaligi va sodiqligidan olishim kerak bo‘lgan tasallini bera olmagan bo‘lar edi. Lekin, men qilgan ishimi hech qachon yuva olmayman.”

Shuningdek amerikalik olimlar Jenica Shorey va Shamekia Thomas aytadiki: “ *Pip mehribon va orzumand. U o‘zining orzu – istaklari sababli kim ekanligini unutdi. Shu sababli eng yaqin insonlardan biri Joga qo‘pol munosabatda bo‘ldi.*”

Bu voqea bosh qahramonning hayotidagi birinchi va achchiq dars bo‘ldi. Albatta, inson bor ekan xato qiladi, ayniqsa yoshlik paytida. Shundan kelib chiqib biz Pipni butunlay qoralayolmaymiz. Pipning Magvitchga yordam bergani, do‘sti Gerbertga o‘z biznesini boshlashida g‘oyibona ko‘maklashishi uning mehribonligidan, sof vijdon egasi ekanligidan darak beradi.

Shunday qilib Pip o‘zining qilgan xatosi va Joning unga munosabati orqali hayotda samimiylik, sodiqlik va mehribonlik kabi hislatlarning qadrini chuqurroq anglab yetadi. Qolaversa, bu tuyg‘ularning boylik, obro‘-e‘tibordan ustun turishini anglagandek bo‘ladi.

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